

ON HYBRID FREE-SPACE OPTIC-RADIO SYSTEMS AS ENABLERS OF 6G SERVICES OVER NON-TERRESTRIAL NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

6G envisions new services such as holographic communications, virtual reality, digital twins, fiber on the sky, augmented reality to name a few of them. These new services will require a large capacity and so, they will be allocated in very high frequency bands, e.g., mmWave, TeraHertz, as well as the optical ones (i.e., fiber and optical wireless). Thus, it is foreseen that 6G will combine free-space optic (FSO) and radio frequency (RF) bands to offer more capacity, resilience to channel impairments and security (e.g. quantum and post-quantum-based security). This paper provides analysis and results on the throughput, and outage probability for the capacity, resilient, and security architectures of hybrid optical-radio systems. For more accuracy, this paper assumes that the optical and radio links have atmospheric impairments—in the optical link, there is a strong turbulence modelled using Gamma-Gamma distribution, whereas in the radio link, there is a fading modelled using Nakagami- m distribution.

Index Terms— 6G, Hybrid Optical-Radio Communication Systems, Free-Space Optics, Non-Terrestrial Networks, Capacity, Resilience, Security, QKD.

1. INTRODUCTION

The sixth generation (6G) communication systems envision to enable new services such as holographic type communications (HTC), tactile internet for remote operations (TIRO), digital twins (DT), space-terrestrial integrated network (STIN), augmented/mixed reality (AR/MR) to name a few them [1]. Furthermore, 6G will resort to quantum and post-quantum security strategies to avoid security breaches from quantum computer attacks. In overall, 6G systems have to: i) provide a larger capacity to satisfy new use cases; ii)

be resilient to the channel impairments to keep the QoS; and iii) increase the security awareness of the communications. Toward this regard, hybrid optical-radio systems is a potential solution to satisfy the capacity, resilience and security that 6G services demand.

In hybrid optical-radio systems for capacity enhancement, different information is sent over the optical and radio links simultaneously. In [2], the joint mutual information of simultaneous data transmission by the optical and radio links is computed. The optical channel is affected by a strong turbulence, whereas the fading of the radio channel is modeled using a Rician distribution. In [3], distinct information is also sent over the optical and radio links in parallel. Results show that considering an initial rate of $R=5$ nats per channel use (npcu), $M=2$ retransmissions, and an outage probability of 10^{-2} , the hybrid optical-radio system reduces the required transmission power by 16 and 4 dB compared to the RF-only and FSO-only links. Additional references of interest on this topic can be found on [4] and [5].

In hybrid optical-radio systems for resilience enhancement, the optical and radio links complement each other against their respective channel impairments. In [6] and [7], the optical link is used as the primary link whereas the radio one is used as a backup. In [6], results show that the use of spatial diversity reduces the switching between the optical and radio communication systems. However, in [7], if the SNR of the optical link is lower than a pre-established threshold, both optical and radio links send the same information. At the receiver, the optical and radio data are combined using Maximum Ratio Combining (MRC) technique. Results show that for a target outage probability of 10^{-6} , the hybrid optical-radio system offers an improvement in transmit power of around 4dB and 5dB over the RF-only and FSO-only schemes respectively. Complementary references on this architecture are also reported on [8], [9].

In hybrid optical-radio systems for security enhancement, the optical link is used to distribute quantum keys, whereas the data channel (i.e., radio, optical fiber, optical wireless) is used to propagate the encrypted information [10]. For large coverage needs, hybrid optical-radio systems may complement fiber-optic networks, i.e., intercontinental links involving satellites [11]. Toward this regard, [12] computes the key

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generation rate in QKD links but introducing atmospheric effects such as the free-space diffraction, atmospheric extinction, fading effects induced by beam wandering, turbulence and pointing errors. Similar works on the topic of key generation rate for QKD can be found in [13] and [14]. However, the previous works do not integrate the quantum-secure part with the capacity and resilient view of hybrid optical-radio systems. On the contrary, the proposed research of this paper integrates them to exploit the full potential of hybrid optical-radio systems for 6G systems.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II details the signal models for the turbulence and fading of the optical and radio links respectively. Sections III explains the architecture and algorithms of hybrid optical-radio systems for capacity, resilience and security respectively. Next, Section IV and V provide its main results and conclusions.

2. SIGNAL MODEL

This section provides the signal models of the optical and radio links as well as the probability density function (PDF) and the cumulative density function (CDF) of the turbulence and fading model for the free-space optic and radio channels.

2.1. Channel model for FSO Links

In this paper, the optical link conveys information modulated in M-APSK symbols. The receiver integrates the signal over each period of time being the received signal formulated as:

$$y_o = \mu I x_o + n_o \quad (1)$$

where x_o represents the optical M-APSK modulated symbols, n_o is an additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with variance σ^2 , μ is the responsivity of the photodiode, and I is the irradiance of the received signal. In FSO, the irradiance I encompasses the effects of the turbulence of the optical channel and it is related with optical SNR, γ_o as: $\gamma_o = \bar{\gamma}_o I^2$. The term $\bar{\gamma}_o$ is the average electrical SNR, and it is defined as: $\bar{\gamma}_o = E_s \mu^2 \eta^2 P_o^2 G_o^2 / \sigma_0^2$ where $E_s, \eta, P_o, \sigma_0^2$, and G_o represent the average symbol energy, modulation index, transmitted optical power, AWG noise variance of photo detection process and optical power attenuation, respectively [15], [16]. This paper considers that there is a strong turbulence between the ground station and the satellite. In this situation, the Gamma-Gamma distribution is used to model the strong optical turbulence [17]. Thus, the irradiance, I , is decomposed into large-scale and small-scale atmospheric effects and its PDF in terms of the optical SNR, γ_o , denoted as $f(\gamma_o)$ is:

$$f(\gamma_o) = \frac{2(\alpha\beta)^{\frac{(\alpha+\beta)}{2}} \gamma_o^{\frac{(\alpha+\beta)}{4}-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)\bar{\gamma}_o^{\frac{(\alpha+\beta)}{4}}} K_{\alpha-\beta} \left(2\sqrt{\alpha\beta} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_o}{\bar{\gamma}_o}} \right), \gamma_o > 0 \quad (2)$$

being Γ the Gamma function, K is the modified Bessel function of the second kind, and the parameters α and β are computed according to [18], [19]. Next, the CDF of (2) is [7]:

$$F(\gamma_o) = \frac{2^{\alpha+\beta-2}}{\pi\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} G_{1,5}^{4,1} \left(\frac{(\alpha\beta)^2 \gamma_o}{16\bar{\gamma}_o} \left| \begin{matrix} 1 \\ \frac{\alpha}{2}, \frac{\alpha+1}{2}, \frac{\beta}{2}, \frac{\beta+1}{2}, 0 \end{matrix} \right. \right) \quad (3)$$

where the symbol G in (3) is the Meijer G function [20].

2.2. Channel model for RF Links

Let P_{RF} be the transmitted power through the RF channel, and $\sqrt{E_s}$ the symbol energy of the constellation, then at the receiving side, the electrical signal is:

$$y_{RF} = \sqrt{E_s} h_{RF} x_{RF} + n_{RF} \quad (4)$$

where x_{RF} is the transmitted modulated RF symbol using complex schemes, e.g. M-QPSK, E_s is the symbol energy, h_{RF} is the RF channel fading and n_{RF} is an i.i.d. Normal random variable whose power is σ_{RF}^2 . The instantaneous received SNR of the RF link is denoted as γ_{RF} is computed as: $\gamma_{RF} = \bar{\gamma}_{RF} h_{RF}^2$, being $\bar{\gamma}_{RF}$ the average SNR of the RF link and h_{RF} is the fading gain. This fading gain has been modeled as a Nakagami- m distribution [2]. By doing so, it is possible to represent a wide majority of realistic Line-of-Sight (LOS) (with high values of the parameter m) and non LOS [21]. Thus, the PDF of γ_{RF} denoted as $f(\gamma_{RF})$, is expressed as [22]:

$$f(\gamma_{RF}) = \frac{\left(\frac{m}{\bar{\gamma}_{RF}}\right)^m \gamma_{RF}^{m-1}}{\Gamma(m)} \exp\left(-m \frac{\gamma_{RF}}{\bar{\gamma}_{RF}}\right), \quad \gamma_{RF} \geq 0 \quad (5)$$

whereas the CDF of (5), $F_{\gamma_{RF}}$, is equated as:

$$F(\gamma_{RF}) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} \gamma \left(m, m \frac{\gamma_{RF}}{\bar{\gamma}_{RF}} \right), \quad \gamma_{RF} \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

where $\gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the regularized (lower) incomplete gamma function of first kind [23].

3. ARCHITECTURE AND ALGORITHMS OF HYBRID OPTICAL-RADIO SYSTEMS

Fig.1 shows the envisioned architecture of the hybrid optical-radio system for 6G demands. The three components of the hybrid optical-radio systems: *capacity*, *resiliency*, and *security* are managed by an Artificial Intelligence (AI) system. However, this AI part is out of the scope of this paper. Let x_o and x_{RF} be the data that the transmitter will send to optical and radio channels, $\gamma_{o,min}$ and $\gamma_{RF,min}$ the minimum SNRs of the optical and radio channels for sending data over them to guarantee a pre-defined QoS, $\hat{\gamma}_o$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{RF}$ the instantaneous SNR of the optical and radio links. Then, the capacity

Fig. 1: Hybrid free space optic-radio architecture as enabler of the capacity (middle), resilience (at the right), and security (at the left) enhancements that 6G systems demand

in hybrid optical-radio systems is expressed as:

$$C_X(\gamma_X) = \sum_{i=1}^Q w_i C_{X,i}(\gamma_X) \quad (7)$$

where in (7) the sub-index X refers to the optical (i.e., X=O) and radio (i.e., X=RF) bands, the index Q is the number of regions in which the SNR of the optical or radio band are subdivided, w_i encompasses the probability that the i -th region of the SNR happens, $C_{X,i}(\gamma_x)$ and $C_X(\gamma_X)$ are the capacities for the i -th region of the SNR of the optical/radio bands and the total one from all regions for a particular SNR γ_X . In order to obtain average results, the instantaneous capacity is normalized by the PDF of the SNR:

$$C_X = \int C_X(\gamma_X) f(\gamma_X) d\gamma_X \quad (8)$$

To determine the capacity, $C_X(\gamma_X)$, the mutual information is maximized. Thus, the mutual information based on the demapper, or the decoder component, M-APSK detected symbols \bar{X} can be calculated as:

$$I(X, \bar{X}) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} \mathbb{E}_{\xi|x_i} \left[\log_2 \left(\frac{M}{1 + e^{\Lambda_{x_i}[\bar{x}_i]}} \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

where ξ represents a Log-Likelihood Ratio realization, M is the number of constellation symbols per modulation, \mathbb{E} is the expectation over $\{X, \bar{X}\}$, $\Lambda_{x_i}[\bar{x}_i]$ is the LLR of symbol x_i for the received decision symbol \bar{x}_i . For the hybrid optical-radio system for capacity enhancement, there are two parallel

yet different flows of data, i.e., $x_o \neq x_{RF}$. So, $\Lambda_{x_i}[\bar{x}_i]$ is computed for the optical and radio links as:

$$\Lambda_{x_i}[\bar{x}_i] = \ln \left(\frac{p(x_i|\bar{x}_i)}{\sum_{j=1; j \neq i}^M p(x_j|\bar{x}_i)} \right)$$

$$\Lambda_{x_i}[\bar{x}_i] = \ln \left(\frac{e^{|y_X - h_X \cdot x_i|^2 / \sigma_X^2}}{\sum_{j=1; j \neq i}^M e^{|y_X - h_X \cdot x_j|^2 / \sigma_X^2}} \right) \quad (10)$$

For hybrid optical-radio system for resilient enhancement, the optical channel is used as main link and the radio one as alternative. However, if the optical channel is slightly degraded and the quality of the radio channel is good, then the same data is sent in parallel through the optical and radio channels, i.e., $x_o = x_{RF}$. At the receiver, the Maximum Ratio Combining (MRC) is used as strategy to detect the transmitted symbols. Next, if the the optical channel is totally degraded and the radio channel is good, then all the information will the transmitted thru the radio link. Lastly, if the SNR conditions of both channels were very bad, then the hybrid optical-radio system would be in outage, i.e., $\hat{\gamma}_o < \gamma_{o,min}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{RF} < \gamma_{RF,min}$. If it is assumed that the optical and radio channels are uncorrelated, then the outage probability of the joint optical-radio system will be the product between the outage probabilities of both links:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{out} &= Pr(\gamma_o < \gamma_{o,min}) Pr(\gamma_{RF} < \gamma_{RF,min}) \\ &= (1 - F(\gamma_{o,min}))(1 - F(\gamma_{RF,min})) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 2: Plot of the (a) throughput, (b) outage probability, and, (c) visibility time of satellite in terms of its inclination

where $F(\gamma_{X,min})$ is the CDF of the optical and radio links (Sec. 2) evaluated at their minimum SNR threshold, $\gamma_{X,min}$.

Regarding, the hybrid optical-radio scheme for security enhancement, it resorts to QKD strategy (see Fig. 1 at the left). QKD systems distribute the keys in optical links using protocols such as BB84, BB92. Nevertheless, their performance may be degraded by atmospheric impairments and so, their quantum key generation rate may be reduced [12]. This is critical since it is necessary to take into account the properties of the data channel, which supports the service to provide. So the quantum and data channels have to be evaluated in a joint way since it is necessary to guarantee: i) the number of available quantum keys during the vision time of the satellite; and ii) the probability of outage for the quantum channel is much lower than the outage probability of the data channel. Let NK be the number of demanded QKD keys and AK the number of available keys at the satellite, then $NK \leq AK$. Otherwise, it is necessary to reuse keys and strategies to increase the security of the satellite constellations are required. For instance, security by design of the satellite orbits (e.g., multi-shell configuration). Thus, let T_S be the vision time of a satellite, T_F the duration of a frame and ρ the fraction of vision time that the information is transmitted. Then, the maximum number of frames that may require a QKD key is: $NK = \rho T_S / T_F$ which has to be much lower than the available keys AK . As it is possible to observe, this is critical in GEO satellites, continuous transmissions ($\rho \rightarrow 1$) and broadband communications ($T_F \rightarrow 0$) since their quantum key generation rate is low, the vision time of the satellite over the user terminal/ground station is permanent ($T_S \rightarrow \infty$) and the duration of the frames is small.

4. RESULTS

To perform the results, the following parameters have been set up. The altitude of the satellite was $H=38000$ km, the wavelength was $\lambda = 1.55 \mu m$, the wind speed was $v=21$ m/s, the altitude of the user equipment was $h_0 = 0$ m, the zenithal angle was $\theta_0=0^\circ$, the alpha and beta parameters were $\alpha = 0.6703$, $\beta = 0.6869$, and the refractive-index coefficient

$Cn^2=2.2 \cdot 10^{-12} m^{-2/3}$ (See [18]), the tested modulation was 4-APSK, and the noise signal was assumed as Gaussian in both links. In hybrid FSO-RF systems for capacity enhancement, the minimum SNR threshold for transmitting over the optical and radio signals for targeting a $BER=10^{-1}$ was $\gamma_{o,min}=20$ dB, and $\gamma_{RF,min}=20$ dB. For FSO-RF systems for resilient enhancement, the FSO and RF systems work simultaneously between 15 and 20 dB. The results show significant improvements on the throughput for both capacity- and resilience-enhanced hybrid systems with respect to the FSO-only and RF-only use cases. In Fig 2.a, the throughput reached 4 bps/Hz, twice the maximum for FSO-only and RF-only systems. While in Fig 2.b, the throughput is better in lower SNRs than FSO-only and RF-only systems. Regarding the outage probabilities, and for target outage probability of 10^{-3} , the use of hybrid optical-radio systems improves 10 dB and 15 dB than the FSO-only and RF-only use cases. Finally Fig 2.c shows the % of the visibility time of a satellite in terms of its inclination when its Latitude is $L=40^\circ$, the beamwidth in Latitude and Longitude are $[10^\circ, 30^\circ]$. From there it is possible to observe that the higher the beamwidth, the larger the visibility time. However, the inclination of the satellite plays a key role. Note that for satellite inclinations close to the polar one the lower the number of keys that the satellite should generate since its visibility time reduces.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study concludes that the use of hybrid optical-radio system has the potential to enhance the capacity, resilience, and security of 6G networks. However, the beam size of the optical and radio beams have to be equivalent. So, in satellite-ground links, the beam size of the optical links should increase to permit the handover between the optical and radio channels. In addition, adaptive optical beams and/or multi-beam optical satellite strategies should be investigated to increase the key generation rates. Finally, an AI system may be used to: i) combat the fading of the optical and radio links; ii) select the hybrid optical-radio working mode; iii) detect the presence of eavesdroppers; and iv) select the quantum keys.

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